

Political Economy of Drinking Water in Rural India: Could Political Will Be Exhibited for the Technical Treatment of Water?

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ABSTRACT: From time immemorial, people in rural areas have developed and depend on natural sources for their socio-economic activities including for drinking purposes. Rural people have developed various sources like tanks, ponds, and wells for their immediate domestic needs, which are open to the sky. Subsequently they depended on springs, rivers, lakes, and irrigational canals for agricultural activities. The post-independent development policies have resorted to piped supply, as part of achieving improved living standards, including health status. The development interventions from the seventies have been focused on meeting rural drinking water needs mostly by extracting water from the ground to fulfil the growing requirements. Undoubtedly, groundwater is now the critical origin households and roughly half of the households depend upon the water fetched from the far distance of their housing premises. It has been a drudgery for the women and girls to walk long distances for the water. Further, the insalubrious reality is that most of the groundwater extracted for drinking purposes is not only untreated at the source of supply but is highly contaminated. The groundwater source is declared with excess iron, excess fluoride, excess salinity, excess nitrate, and excess arsenal, which are awkwardly reasoned out for multiple health hazards. With over one-third of the rural habitations inflicted with waterborne diseases for consumption of untreated water, public interventions have hardly given serious consideration to the quality dimension. Especially, attempts to treat the drinking water are altogether missing. This insensitive attitude is nothing less than throwing health consideration of the rural masses at risk besides breaking the rural (or rather Indian) economy. However, the reinvigorated interventions in recent times have given some ray of hopes to escape from health risks. This research highlights all the challenges of rural drinking water issues and brings to the fore public interventions for immediate remedial and corrective actions.

KEYWORDS: Basic Need, Drinking Water, Global Concerns, Rural India, Major Challenges, Policy Implications

JEL: P25, Q25, R38, R58

INTRODUCTION: Drinking water though a critical lifeline of all lives ever since civilization's existence, most societies have attached unparalleled importance to the supply of this critical input for human and animal existence notwithstanding divergences. However, while supplying drinking water (if not safe and assured quality), the organizational mechanisms created have not only limited meeting the critical need but have caused several inconveniences to the people. Especially, it has been the case for those living in backward regions and rural areas, as they are domiciling away from the "So-Called" civilized but urban world and are not generally assertive for want of education and information. This apart, the development interventions and the organizational mechanisms thus created have also divided the human settlements into self-sufficient and deprived segments more than any measure. With the quality of the water always in question in the deprived segments, discrimination in the provision of safe water supply is the hallmark even to date. With these parallel situations, the disadvantaged settlements have obviously resorted to using contaminated water for drinking, without any escape or water treatments. Unfortunately, the water supply interventions more so the public authorities have turned blind eyes to the various ramifications for drinking contaminated water and in regards to the health hazards that would be caused owing to the incidence. These situations exist in such pockets of the human settlements necessarily backward despite the various international declarations for over four decades to supply potable, treated, and healthy water to all and commitments of the nation's states. Interestingly, the concerns of the international community, especially the United Nations have been playing an unparalleled role since 1976 (or since more than four decades) to ensure the supply of quality drinking water to all and to ensure good health to all. The essence of these four declarations have been the critical means to view

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drinking water as a basic need of mankind and other lives forever and shall be part of the organized human arrangements in every living environment. With this, it can be even said that there cannot be any human settlement without a water source for various needs, including drinking. Also, safe drinking water and sanitation have been attached importance as central to living conditions and good health of the people. Thus, these two fundamentals have become a significant weighty part of the sustainable goal for the public development interventions of any country in putting appropriate drinking water systems in place for the people (Table 1).

The first-ever attempt of international concern was importance of drinking water and sanitation to all over the conference on human settlements. The outcomes have not only sensitized the member nations of the United Nations but laid a strong foundation and paved the way for the declaration of a decade exclusively for drinking water and sanitisation. The conference considered drinking water as a welfare good for the people within the housing infrastructure and housing services (UNs 1976). Second was the World Health Organisation Report (WHO 1993) pointed to the fact that in eight countries of the South-East Asia Region (SEAR) 80 percent of the people persist/dwell the rural areas have been vulnerable to risk with very poor drinking water and sanitation systems. The lack of sufficient safe water supplies and sanitation has led to water-borne diseases in the region. Diarrhoeal diseases of children and severe malnutrition incidences are the major contributors to the high proportion of infant mortality. Typhoid, Dysentery, cholera, and amoebic infections are widely prevalent in the case of adults in the SEA region. Keeping these observations in view, the declaration has highlighted that 87 percent of the population to be served with a safe water supply by the turn of the decade. The third attempt was to account for the necessities of the people living in disadvantaged pockets (rural, backward, and small towns) depending on standpipes, boreholes with hand pumps, and protected dug wells, given the limited access to piped water supplies. It is needless to say these sources are considered as contaminated water with excess chemicals and other materials, which is hazardous to the health of the people. However, it has also been sensitized at the same time that government, public authorities, and international agencies should change their approach and their commitments to supplying safe and adequate drinking water (Habitat 1996). Most importantly, the approach to drinking water shall be from total households and habitations

Table 1: Global Concerns on Safe Drinking Water

Organization and Year	Name of the Declaration	Basis of the Declaration	Objectives of the Declarations
United Nations - 1976	First Conference on Human Settlements (Vancouver, Canada)	Essentially highlighted the importance of improving water supply and sanitation to all.	To sensitize the global declaration on Water Supply and Sanitation and to ensure the same by the member nations to their population.
World Health Organisation (WHO) - 1983	International Drinking Water Supply and Sanitation Decade (IDWSSD:1981-1991)	As a basic need of human beings and other lives.	To meet the drinking water needs of all the ill-served population in the rural areas, problematic villages, uncovered towns, and urban areas.
United Nations Centre for Human Settlements (Habitat) - 1996	Global Report on Human Settlements 1996: An Urbanizing World	As part of the orderly human settlements, good housing, living conditions, and health. Also, Drinking water is part of the good social infrastructure.	To ensure clean and safe water for all with the support of technology as solutions to decontaminate the drinking water and to cover the uncovered people with an organized water supply.
United Nations - 2015	Transforming Our World: The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development (Popularly	To transform the world free of poverty, and disease, ensure health care, social protection, assured social well-being, human right to safe drinking water, improved	The goal is set to be realized by 2030; To end child mortality, water-borne diseases, and other tropical diseases;

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	Sustainable Development Goals)	hygiene, safe and sustainable human habitats, and others. Two of the seventeen goals emphasize on ensuring healthy lives, promoting well-being for all, ensure availability and sustainable water for all.	To achieve universal and equitable access to safe and affordable drinking water for all; To improve water quality by eliminating hazardous chemicals and contaminated materials; To increase water-use efficiency, integrated water resource management; and To conserve all its eco-systems of water including aquifers, lakes, ponds, etc.
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Source: Compiled by the author from the respective documents.

coverage in the first instance to quality improvement of the water in the second stage, with enhanced public investment in the technological applications. Fourth and the last serious and declared concern is to putting an end to all forms of poverty, and diseases and promoting health, ensuring social protection and social well-being. For the first time, an exclusive human rights dimension is contemplated by the United Nations report to provide safe drinking water and improved hygiene apart from bringing about safe and sustainable human habitats and environments. While setting the goals, the United Nations suggested two very significant inputs to the member nations' governments: (a) Appropriate, Concrete Policies and Action Programmes for the supply of safe drinking water; and (b) Global Partnership between the advanced and progressing countries for sustainable development. It has further suggested harnessing resource mobilization from developed countries, capacity building, and transfer of environmentally sound technologies to developing countries. In this regard, it is observed that developed countries should implement their commitment to Official Development Assistance (ODA) of 0.7 percent of the gross national income of developing countries and 0.15 to 0.20 percent to the least developed countries. Enhancing international support for capacity building to implement all the SDGs and similarly, promoting the development, transfer, dissemination, and diffusion of environmentally sound technologies to developing countries in favourable terms have been the other concerns. Also, debt relief and debt restructuring, as appropriate policies shall be offered to highly indebted poor countries to reduce debt distress, and to facilitate the implementation of the goal effectively.

Ever since the growing concerns on drinking water, India too had committed to live up to all the decisions if not fully, as a member nation. It has exhibited its concerns of the IDWSSD: 1981-1991 goals from 1981 as well as primary health care for achieving Health for all by 2000. Having constituted a National Apex Committee for the purpose, it did not design any policy priority in place as far as drinking water is concerned. But yet targeted to cover 100 percent of water at 75 Litres per capita per Day (LPCD) and 25 percent sanitation in rural areas. Subsequently, the 1982 conference of all state heads decided to put sound policies to serve the ill-served population with appropriate technology, service level, and community involvement, as part of the implementation of the Decadal programmes. It is also decided to prioritise problematic villages, and non-problem villages and provision of rural sanitation. Further, as noted already the people with coverage for treated drinking water is a little more than one-third, which leaves a substantial portion to entirely depend upon the untreated and highly contaminated water sources. The effective policies and public actions for water treatment with the help of technology, as the concern expressed. What disappoints further is the uncovered people water network system, which is officially in the order of over 11 percent. These people could be living in the mountains, forests, or areas completely disconnected from the core settlements. With these backdrops of the international concerns and India's responses, this paper highlights the contemporary situation with a few objectives: (a) to present drinking water scenario in terms of the coverage of the households; (b) to throw light on the quality issues in the system; (c) to highlight the new initiatives of Swajaldhara and Jal Jeevan Mission (JJM) for rural areas; (d) to propose a few policy inferences for areas intervention to bring about healthy water supply for rural India. The paper used the official data source and public information to reflect on its objectives, especially the published data of the Census of India, information from the Ministry of Rural Development, and the various website details on the issues discussed.

Coverage of Habitations & Households: India is a country of over 6.49 lakh villages with as many as 16.78 crores of households domiciling, out of the total number of 24.67 crores households (Census 2011). It is in the order of over 68 percent of the total, even though urbanization has been increasing at a faster rate in recent times. Although the absolute the number has increased from 13.83 crores, in relative terms, the same has dwindled from over 73 percent. Straightforwardly, in effect 4 percent have

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reduced in the recent time. Similarly, the housing stock in rural areas constitutes 15.99 crores or 68 percent of the total number of 23.61 crores. Coincidentally, the relative share in housing stock has also dropped by 4 points from 72 percent (Mahadeva 2020). India is known for developing its native models for its livelihood sustenance and in the arena of meeting its basic needs with very limited external influence, more so in developing drinking water sources and systems. Although drinking water is not a basic need but is a lifeline for both human and animal beings. The native models built over several centuries have both met the needs majority of the Indians and the other walks of life. Undoubtedly, the fact is that even today the native models are continuing to play a critical part in the rural context.

The schematic intervention for the supply of drinking water in rural areas dates back to the early seventies. This points to the fact that until early seventies neither the total need was assessed nor did the government intervene. As per the Constitution of India, the primary responsibility of providing water for various activities, including for drinking purposes rests with the State List, under the Seventh Schedule of Clause 17 (Bare Act 2015). Considering the magnitude of the need, the Government of India supplements the efforts of the state governments by providing financial assistance under the National Rural Drinking Water Programme (NRDWP) introduced in 1973. To give further impetus, an exclusive Department of Drinking Water Supply under the Ministry of Rural Development was created in 1999 with a mission approach for the purpose. Earmarking 20 percent of the annual outlay towards the reform projects, the NRDWP has been a landmark as it led to covering the entire country under “Swajaldhara – roughly Self Water Supply”. Especially after the constitutional 73rd amendment in 1993, coverage of habitations, quality problems in drinking water, and sustainability of sources & systems have been the major thrust of the sector. Importantly, the norm is to supply 55 litres per capita per day (LPCD) - with a source within 0.5 km in the plain and 50 meters’ elevation in the hill areas in all rural habitations, against the earlier prescription of 40 LPCD with a source within 1.6 km. Minimizing the distance is found to be a very big relief to the people, more so to the women.

Coverage of habitations and rural households are extremely important aspects from the viewpoint of meeting a critical human need by fulfilling basic needs, besides advancing social development. Being critical lifeline of mankind and animals, which directly determines their health status. It may not be wrong to say all civilized settlements have taken place only nearer or alongside water bodies. Drinking water requirements, supply, and management issues are entirely different from those in the urban context. Water is a household need, from which is mostly ensured within the housing premises or the reachable distance, after fetching from long distances in urban areas. Apart from the household requirement (if not the same quantity), water is essential for household animal rearing and maintenance, and other purposes. The situation is also entirely different regarding the sources of water availability and households’ dependence in rural areas, as the households meet the needs from multiple untreated sources, mostly away from the residences. But in urban areas, the drinking water is managed by an exclusive department, which manages to fetch the water from long distances, stores it in elevated areas, and distribute the same to all households at time intervals. But, drinking water is arranged and distributed customarily by the overhead tanks through the piped network in nearby or central places in rural areas. In other words, supplying water to individual households with the piped network is altogether a new intervention of the government, of which the achievement progress is tardy.

It is evident from Table 2 that rural households meet their drinking water needs typically from multiple sources in the absence of adequate development intervention, especially piped networks. What disappoints the fifty-year-old intervention in the supply of clean drinking water has covered only a little above one-third of the rural households, leaving the majority of households to unclean water sources. Supply of treated tap water has covered only 38 percent of the households hitherto and as a result of the tardy progress, the rest of the households are depending on untreated water sources. Hand pumps and tube wells are the major untreated water sources but they have been the critical source of drinking water to over two-thirds of the rural households. Also, household-covered wells have been continuing to meet the drinking water needs of a good chunk of the households. Further apart from the three critical sources, open sources like uncovered wells, springs, rivers, canals, tanks, ponds, and lakes have also been playing a significant part in meeting the drinking water needs. It may not be wrong to say that these open sources have been catering largely to the animals and some extent even the domestic requirements. It must also be bear in mind that there are overlapping between the treated and untreated water resources while registering the progress. Strictly cannot be said that households depending on treated water do not use the untreated sources for their needs or vice versa. But, what determines the dependence on the alternative source is the adequacy of the principal water sources. Further and equally important issue is the source of availability of water - within the premises, near the premises, or away from the premises. The commonest practice is fetching drinking water from far away distance and disappointingly, the scenario is continuing even after seventy-five years of independence. Equally noticeable is the women who walk the distance to fetch the water from the far distance, in addition to her other household chores. The scenario not only mirrors the casual attitude of the development intervention but also of the development gap in meeting human needs. The table depicts that about one-fourth of the households

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fetch drinking water from far distance from the premises, in the absence of its non-availability within the premises or near the premises. The issue of fetching drinking water from far distance is quite similar across the various sources. Although the incidence is half of the total in the case of the treated tap water, the other sources have registered the same scale by and large. However, in the case of the open sources, more than double the average incidence of the households recorded have been fetching water from far away distance or ferrying the animals to the water sources, which is a burdensome as well as time-consuming process. In other words, the rest of the households supply drinking water to the animals within and near the premises. Yet another scenario is the water availability near the housing premises. Roughly 43 percent of the rural households depend on the nearby source, which again speaks of the deficiency in the water supply intervention. Lastly, only a little above one-third of the households have had the benefit of drinking water within the housing premises, although the progress is tardy viewing from the viewpoint of the length of the development intervention. However, the literature has attributed several reasons for the tardy progress like increasing population, increasing number of habitations, outlived water supply system, poor maintenance, depleting ground water table, etc.

Table 2: Drinking Water Scenario in Rural India (Percentage)

Sources of Drinking Water	Total Households	Within the Premises	Near the Premises	Away from Premises
Households by All Sources	68.03	35.01	42.93	22.06
Treated Tap Water	38.00	50.00	39.56	10.44
Untreated Tap Water	76.18	39.27	48.57	12.16
Covered Well	6.52	43.15	32.23	24.62
Hand Pump/Tube Well	88.68	32.85	45.01	22.14
Open Sources (Well, Spring, River, Canal, Tank, Pond and Lake)	85.12	11.81	39.18	49.01
Others	62.44	-	37.55	62.45

Source: Census of India (2011), Tables on Houses, Household Amenities and Assets, Series 1, Registrar General and Census Commissioner, India.

Quality Problems of the Rural Water Supply: One of the very serious concerns of the rural drinking water supply is the quality of water, notwithstanding the coverage of the households. The disappointing reality has been that the drinking water mostly being served is not treated but is contaminated in a good number of rural habitats. This situation has led to an increasing incidence of health issues and health hazards. In this regard, the background paper on the Rural Water Supply Sector by the

Table 3: Nature of Quality Problems in Rural Water Supply

Sl. No	Nature of Quality Problem	Number of Habitations	Immediate Effects	Solutions Suggested for Public Actions
01	Excess Iron	1,18,088	The human body cannot easily absorb iron from water which makes it harder to get rid of harmful bacteria	Passing the water through a cartridge or backwashing filter and followed by a water softener are the commonest solutions.
02	Excess Fluoride	31,306	Bone damage in all forms like arthritis, joint problems, and many others.	Reverse Osmosis filtration system to remove over 85 percent of fluoride. It can be used at the household and community supply system level.
03	Excess Salinity	23,495	Excess salt content causes hypertension or high blood pressure, which leads to high risks of stroke.	Good groundwater recharge, planting, native vegetation, striking balance between water recharge and water discharge where possible.
04	Excess Nitrate	13,958	Increase hardness in the water. High-level nitrates in drinking	Reverse Osmosis and Distillation removes nitrate from drinking water. Ion Exchange

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			water may increase the risk of colon cancer	Units operate much like household water softeners.
05	Excess Arsenal	5,029	Recurring diarrhea, thickening of the skin, discoloration of the skin, Nausea, Abnormal heart rhythm, Numbness in hands and feet, Partial paralysis, small corns, etc.	Domestic Reverse Osmosis (RO) is found to be an effective method for atomic scale filtration.
06	Multiple Quality Problems	25,092	All the above ailments at varied scales and incident	
Total		2, 16, 968 or 13 percent of the total rural habitations of 16, 66, 075, as per the Rural Habitations Survey Bulletin of DDWS, Ministry of Rural Development.		

Source: Government of India, Ministry of Rural Development, Department of Drinking Water Supply, Rural Water Supply Sector: Background Paper. The immediate effects and solutions suggested for the quality issues are downloaded from the various websites.

Ministry of Rural Development itself has rightly identified and accounted for the incidence and nature of the quality problems across the rural habitations. Also, it has cautioned about waterborne diseases, health risks, and threats to the people in the long run, if the untreated sources is not treated with appropriate interventions and technology. Thanks to the background paper of the ministry, which is an eye opener and exposes the gravity of the situation, though the maximum limits of contents are not indicated. But for the background paper, the issue of rural water supply would not have claimed public attention for the protection of health. Excessive dependence on untreated water for drinking purposes in rural areas has a direct bearing on the health status of the people. Accordingly, as many as 2.17 lakh rural habitations (13 percent) of the 16.66 lakhs have been depending on the contaminated drinking water, with five major contents and elements like excessive iron, excessive fluoride, excessive salinity, excessive Nitrate, and excessive arsenal (Table 3). Of all the elements, although iron content is helpful to human organisms' excess iron content in the water results in the human body not absorbing iron from water easily and makes it harder to get rid of harmful bacteria, as the literature suggests. Excess iron content in the water is observed in over 1.18 lakh habitations or 56 percent of the total habitations facing the quality issue. Further, excess content of iron also leads to a metallic taste in the water, food, and beverages, besides causing stains on dishes, laundry, plumbing fixtures, etc. Similarly, excess fluoride in drinking water is found in more than thirty thousand habitations that straightforwardly result in bone damage, arthritis, joint-related problems, dental and skeletal fluorosis, fatigue, and chronicle issues apart from affecting kidneys and liver functions. High levels of salts in drinking water affect the taste of water, as sodium and chloride are predominant in it and reduce the suitability to drink. High level of nitrate is a result of runoff or leakage from fertilized soil, wastewater, landfills, animal feedlots, septic systems, or urban drainage. Cancer risk is the most serious adverse effect of nitrate intake. Lastly, long-term exposure to arsenic from drinking water and food can cause cancer, cardiovascular disease, and diabetes, apart from negatively impacting cognitive development and increased deaths in young adults. Also, more than two lakh rural habitations (over 13 percent) have been identified with the quality problems of the drinking water, their immediate effects and possible solutions are detailed in the table. Regrettably, barring a small write-up about the quality problems of the drinking water in rural areas, the public failure to broadcast about the ill effects of the same is very conspicuous. It should have been made known through the village panchayats or the effective solutions as suggested against quality problems should have been at each village level in different places. Imparting education about the quality of drinking water and health issues associated with the same is the need of the hour, if at all natural justice to be delivered by the governments at all levels. Also, from the viewpoint of the background paper and addressing the crises in the rural areas, what is needed is the corrective action to ensure safe and quality drinking water in rural areas.

Sustainable Rural Water Sources for Drinking

Swajaldhara: Groundwater is the principal source for drinking as well as irrigation in the rural areas in many states of the country. This source meets over 85 percent of the irrigation and drinking water needs of more than two-thirds of rural households. Uninterrupted extraction of groundwater for both purposes has caused depletion drastically and as a result, the background paper of the ministry has estimated that the water table has declined by one foot every year in several states. At this juncture and as part of the sustainability of the system, the national government has encouraged the Water Users (WUs) with grants of incentives up to 20 percent of the Accelerated Rural Water Supply Programme (ARWSP). WUs have been entrusted with the responsibilities

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to manage and institutionalize community participation in the rural drinking water programs, besides ensuring full participation of the villagers in the project decision-making, design, implementation, and management of the physical scheme of the rural water supply of their choice. Four important tasks are assigned to the 'Water and Sanitation Committees' at the Gram Panchayat level: (a) to create awareness and train all the stakeholders; (b) to build capacity at the village level; (c) to share the capital cost of ten percent either in cash or kind (labour land, material); and (d) to take up rainwater harvesting and groundwater recharge structures. The swajaldhara with all the features embedded to take up water conservation and recharge measures for source strengthening of drinking water. The community contribution (10 percent) is believed to bring in the ownership of the water supply scheme. A major impetus was laid under Bharat Nirman to attend to the quality problem of the uncovered and slipped-back habitations and over 4.5 lakh habitations were covered. Further, the present promulgation in rural areas is to:

- Achieve household-level drinking water security by assessing proper water demand;
- Strengthen the sustainability measures by focusing development of multi-sources (surface water, groundwater, and rainwater harvesting) by minimizing the single water source;
- Water conservation methods including the revival of traditional water bodies like tanks, lakes, ponds, etc.;
- Conscious move to rainwater harvesting to tackle fluoride contamination, instead of high-cost treatment technologies for Arsenic and Fluoride contaminations;
- Solar desalination and dilution through rainwater harvesting to tackle salinity problems; and
- Treatment of catchment area by fencing and effective Total Sanitation Campaign programme, prevention of sewage and animal waste leaching into the surface and underground water source, and promotion of ecological sanitation for nitrate contamination.

Jal Jeevan Mission: As a follow-up action of the Swajaldhara programme promulgations and in the backdrop of the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (UNSDGs), the Government of India revisited public action to ensure the availability of safe drinking water. Indeed, important to note that ensuring adequate and quality drinking water is part of ending poverty (Goal 1), promoting healthy lives and well-being (Goal 3), ensuring availability of water for all (Goal 6), reducing inequalities (Goal 10) and a few others dealing with women causes, strongly emphasized in the UNSDGs (United Nations 2015). Jal Jeevan Mission (JJM) was introduced after subsuming the existing National Rural Drinking Water Programme (NRDWP), introduced in 2019 with its vision and mission. The JJM has a vision to ensure quality drinking water supply (as per BIS: 10500) and adequate quantity of 55 LPCD to every rural household regularly on a long-term basis to improve the status of the communities. Ending age-old drudgery faced by women and young girls in the collection of drinking water from far-distance sources is the added vision of the JJM. The other vision is to reduce the rural-urban divide and to enhance public health (PIB 2024). These three visions would not only enhance water quantity as against the earlier prescription of 40 LPCD but also bring huge relief to rural women. To be a reality, the government has allocated a huge budget of Rs. 3.6 Lakh Crores for the mission. The intent of the mission has been to cover 16 crore additional rural households with Individual Household Tap Connections (IHTC) by 2024, against only 3.23 crore (17 percent) in 2019. The JJM has six very important interventional components: (a) water quality improvement to reduce water-borne ailments; (b) source sustainability by promoting groundwater recharge and water conservation; (c) grey water management by reusing and recycling water for source sustenance; (d) skill development and employment generation for local people in maintaining water supply structures; (e) bottom-up planning, implementation, operations, and management by community engagement, particularly women as the key stakeholder, and; (f) focus on future generations by supplying tap water to schools, tribal hostels, Anganwadi (daycare) centers.

Upfront, it must be noted that India is still rural with over two-thirds of its population lives, although urbanization is growing at a fast pace with sprawling economic opportunities for the people, which has attracted rural workforce migration in recent times (Mahadeva 2022). Also important is that protecting the health of the rural Indians is as paramount as the Indian economy itself, given their contributions to food security, livelihood, workforce segments, and what not. From the provision of safe and adequate rural drinking water, the government cannot afford to attach subsidiary importance for its availability. Because water is the lifeline, a critical basic human need, and a parameter of social development indicator of the country. To ensure the same, the JJM has been aimed at achieving laudable objectives of (a) providing Functional Household Tap Connection (FHTC) to every rural household, especially in the quality-affected areas, drought-prone regions and desert areas; (b) providing functional tap connections in schools, Anganwadi (pre-school) centres, gram panchayats and community buildings, health and wellness centres; (c) monitoring the functionality of tap connections by promoting voluntary ownership among the local community; (d) developing sustainability in the water supply systems, water sources, water infrastructure and regular funding for operations and maintenance; and (e) developing and empowering human resources covering water quality management, water treatment,

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catchment protection, plumbing, construction and electrical works. With the public initiatives including the JJM, as discussed have played a significant part in improving the drinking water situation in rural areas (Bassi et al 2022).

It is appropriate to note that against a dismal performance of only 17 percent household coverage with tap connections, the JJM has achieved a significant proportion of success with its vision and mission. It has claimed to have covered 15.07 crores rural household with FHTC of drinking water by August 2024, out of the current total number of 19.34 crores of rural households. The total coverage of households is around 78 percent with FHTC. In effect, the mission has covered a total number of 12.24 crore households with IHTCs during the six years of its period, milestone achievement. This leaves the other 22 per cent or 1.03 crore of households to be covered, in the days to come. The institutional coverage with tap connections is 22.90 lakhs (Schools 9.30 Lakhs, Anganwadis 9.67 Lakhs and Public institutions 3.93 lakhs). Further, 2,160 water testing laboratories have been established to undertake water testing in rural areas, and reportedly 24.64 lakh women have been trained to use Field Test Kits (FTK) to test the quality of drinking water at homes. However, despite these milestones achieved and 100 per cent coverage of households in good number of states and union territories, JJM has beset with a few challenges like lack of dependable water sources, groundwater contamination uneven geographical terrain, scattered rural habitations and other administrative issues. These issues need serious considerations to fulfil the target 'No one should be left out' in the rural areas

Concluding Observations: From the above analysis, it is apparently clear that rural households have been dependent upon multiple water sources for drinking and other activities, principally hand pumps for domestic and open sources for other needs. If hand pumps are the public initiative mainly, some of the open sources have been created by rural communities. Also, deceptively true that the water from these sources is untreated and contaminated with excessive chemicals, which has health implications for rural communities. Furthermore, these factual situations have paved for reinvigorated interventions in the recent times, which have resulted in bringing few respites in the coverage of rural households for water supply in large numbers and releasing women-related drudgery. Apart from accounting for the external concerns on improving the drinking water conditions in rural areas, three broad issues can be brought to the fore. First, the public authorities want the main stakeholders i.e., rural people and rural communities to manage the water sources on a sustainable basis with limited financial resources in their control, including the vertical transfers. Since rural communities own a few of the water sources, what is needed is education, training, and information on sustainable maintenance strategies at panchayat levels. Secondly, excessive dependence untreated water sources and open sources by the rural communities should not distance public authorities from their responsibilities, as have been elusive in creating healthy lives and environments. They shall do their part in terms of adequate financial transfers from time to time, Proper maintenance and monitoring water eco system and community involvement until ensuring quality drinking water to all. Thirdly, with almost no public expenditure till 2019 for technical capacity building at the panchayat level, technical interventions for drinking water treatment were altogether missing and was a distant dream for the rural communities. Substantive actions, especially for the development of water treatment infrastructure in every nook and corner were completely lacking. It may not be wrong to say that success does not lies in providing unsafe and health-hazardous water to rural households but technical treatment of the same. These arguments of failures are conspicuously true as long as the existence of excess Arsenic, Fluoride, Salinity, and Nitrate in the drinking water sources. It only reflects upon the absence of adequate and appropriate public development measures to remove the elements of contamination in the drinking water of majority of the Indians. The immediate implication is that it is a casual attitude of the public authorities, besides continued desertion and mistreatment of the people in general and the health aspects of the rural Indians in particular. Further, the continued treatment of the rural Indians as unfortunate and ill-fated citizens, as has happened in the last several decades of independence which is highly discriminatory and prejudiced. Therefore, it seriously calls for a change in the attitude of the public authorities to put in place appropriate action to meet the critical needs of safe drinking water for rural Indians, if not as comfort. This is necessarily meant to improve the water quality by appropriate technical treatment measures, as a need of the hour. There is an urgent need to exhibit political will for wellness of the rural Indians in this regard.

Drinking water is undoubtedly a merit good of society and ensuring clean, safe, healthy, and quality water for all households involves economic cost, which requires political motivation or consensus. Providing safe water for the majority of rural households demands huge public investment and this becomes a reality if political solidarity is expressed. The immediate challenge before the policymakers is to find a feasible and realistic solution to the provision of safe water technically to all rural households. With necessary public financial commitment to establish technical water treatment plants in multiple numbers in every rural habitation for the removal of all the contaminating elements. As the researchers point out, the need is to establish/install water softeners to remove hardness in the water and to bring down the iron content to a tolerable level. Similarly, reverse osmosis technologies need to be adopted to remove excess fluoride, nitrate, and arsenic at the community sources and end point of rural

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households, with fiscal incentives and subsidies. Earmarking Rs. 3.6 lakh crores under JJM is a landmark decision of the national government, which should be sustained until the rural public health is achieved. Further, rainwater harvesting on a massive scale is suggested to be the solution for the removal of excess salinity, apart from the development of native vegetation in every habitation. These corrective actions are imminent from rural communities in the problematic habitations with high incidence of drinking water contamination. It must be undertaken on a war footing basis at the cost of the public exchequer. It may not be inappropriate to suggest that having attained almost total coverage of households in the first stage, technical treatment of the drinking water in every rural habitation shall be the priority in the next stage, to ensure the quality of the drinking water. Otherwise, the purpose of bringing out the background status paper by the ministry would be defeated, if the government does not incur public expenditure to develop the necessary water treatment mechanisms at a large scale in rural areas. It must also be borne in mind that after diagnosing the quality problems in the drinking water, public authorities, including the governments cannot afford to play with the health of the rural majoritarian. Above all, the pertinent question is how the government can afford to take a different stand as far as drinking water quality in rural India is concerned. Being a member nation of the United Nations, India owes to fulfill all the agenda goals by 2030 to ensure healthy lives, promote well-being, and ensure potable water for all on sustainable management of the sources. This invariably calls for massive but corrective public actions with public investment in drinking water sector.

From all the above perspectives, the need is to sensitize the rural Indians about drinking water contaminations, public corrective actions (antidotes), peoples' responsibilities and participation, public expenditure, in the management of the water sources, and all the other aspects. The sensitization shall be undertaken by the Gram Panchayats on a massive scale to all the stakeholders in all the villages, apart from advertisements, broadcasting, and campaigns through media for the benefit of people in the villages and the benefits of the Indian economic systems. In particular, corrective actions with a priority to improve the quality of drinking water technically is an immediate need at each settlement in rural areas, given the serious level of water contamination and its health implications for the people. The JJM being a transformative initiative, apart from covering all the rural households with IHTC/FHTC needs to focus on technical treatment of drinking water at source to ensure quality. The political will demonstrated in the resource allocation for rural drinking water sector must be continued till fulfilling the basic need of the rural Indians. Sufficient development of the technical infrastructure for water treatment, including the technical human resources should be prioritised for sustainable quality water supply. Rural households should also be incentivised with subsidies for technical care of the drinking water at the end user level.

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